

MAJORIZATION OF MATRICES

S. Manimaran*, V. Chinnadurai & A. Swaminathan*****

* Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, SRMKV College,
Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, Annamalai University,
Annamalainagar, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, Aksheyaa College of
Engineering, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

It is shown that under certain conditions the column majorization of matrices is reversed for the column majorization of their corresponding Moore-Penrose inverses and preserved for the column majorization of their powers. The condition for column majorization of block matrices is determined.

Index Terms: Majorization & Moore-Penrose inverse

1. Introduction:

Let $C^{m \times n}$ denote the space of $m \times n$ complex matrices. If $A \in C^{m \times n}$ then the Moore-Penrose inverse A^+ of A is the unique solution to the equations:

$$AXA = A, \quad XAX = X, \quad (AX)^* = AX \quad \text{and} \quad (XA)^* = XA \quad [2, p.7].$$

A square matrix A is called *EP* if $R(A) = R(A^*)$ or equivalently $AA^+ = A^+A$, where $R(A)$ denotes the range space of A . A matrix A is called EP_r if A is EP and is of rank r .

Let $R^{m \times n}$ denotes the space of $m \times n$ real matrices. For any column vector $x \in R^n$, let $x_{[1]}, x_{[2]}, \dots, x_{[n]}$ denote the coordinates of x arranged in decreasing order of magnitude: $x_{[1]} \geq x_{[2]} \geq \dots \geq x_{[n]}$. We shall write $x \downarrow = (x_{[1]}, x_{[2]}, \dots, x_{[n]})^t$ where t denotes the transpose. If $x, y \in R^n$, we say that y is majorized by x , denoted $y \prec x$ if

$$\sum_{i=1}^k y_i = \sum_{i=1}^k x_i, \quad \text{for } 1 \leq k \leq n-1, \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n y_i = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

Also y is said to be majorized by x if and only if there exists a doubly stochastic matrix M such that $y = Mx$ [4, p.7-12]. Throughout this paper we consider only real matrices.

2. Majorization of Matrices:

The majorization of vectors is extended to matrices as follows:

Definition 1:

Let A and B be $m \times n$ real matrices. Then A is said to be column majorized by B , denoted by $A \prec^c B$ if and only if $A = MB$ where M is a doubly stochastic matrix of order m .

We note that the column majorization of matrices is equivalent to the majorization of the transpose of the corresponding matrices [4, p.430].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i.e. } A \prec^c B &\Leftrightarrow A = MB, \quad \text{where } M \text{ is doubly stochastic} \\ &\Leftrightarrow A = MB \quad \text{for all } i, \text{ where } A_i \text{ is the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ column of } A \\ &\Leftrightarrow A_i^t = B_i^t \quad \text{for all } i \\ &\Leftrightarrow A^t \prec B^t. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1:

Let A, B be EP_r matrices and $A \prec^c B$. Then $R(A) = R(B)$ and $(AB)^+ = B^+ A^+$.

Proof:

$$A \prec^c B \Rightarrow A = MB \Rightarrow N(B) \subseteq N(A) \quad \text{where } N(A), \text{ denotes the null space of } A.$$

Since A and B are EP_r , $R(A) = R(B)$, then by theorem 3 of [1], AB is EP_r and by theorem 4 of [1], we get $(AB)^+ = B^+A^+$.

Lemma 2:

Let A be an EP matrix. Then

(i) $A \prec^c A^+A \Leftrightarrow A^+A \prec^c A^+$

(ii) $A^+A \prec^c A \Leftrightarrow A^+ \prec^c A^+A$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \cdot (i) A \prec^c A^+A &\Leftrightarrow A = MA^+A \\ &\Leftrightarrow AA^+ = MA^+AA^+ \text{ (on post multiplication by } A^+ \text{ or } A) \\ &\Leftrightarrow AA^+ = MA^+ \text{ (since } A \text{ is } EP \text{ and } A^+AA^+ = A^+) \\ &\Leftrightarrow A^+A \prec^c A^+ \end{aligned}$$

Hence the result (i). Similarly (ii) can be proved.

Remark 1:

In particular, if A is nonsingular, then $A \prec^c I \Leftrightarrow I \prec^c A^{-1}$. Hence $A \prec^c I \Rightarrow A \prec^c A^{-1}$. If the column sums of A is one, then $I \prec^c A^{-1}$, however A need not be a doubly stochastic matrix.

Remark 2:

We note that the condition on A cannot be relaxed in the above lemma 2. For example,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & A^+ &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ AA^+ &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & A^+A &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Here A is not EP , however $A \prec^c A^+A$ and $A^+A \prec^c A^+$.

Remark 3:

For any EP matrix A , if $A \prec^c I$, then $A = AA^+A \prec^c A^+A$. Hence by lemma 2 $A \prec^c A^+A \prec^c A^+$. In particular if A is EP and doubly stochastic, then $A \prec^c I$ holds automatically and hence $A \prec^c A^+A \prec^c A^+$

Theorem 1:

If A is EP_r and B is symmetric idempotent with rank r , then

(i) $A \prec^c B \Leftrightarrow B^+ \prec^c A^+$

(ii) $B \prec^c A \Leftrightarrow A^+ \prec^c B^+$

(iii) $A \prec^c B \Rightarrow A \prec^c A^+$

(iv) $B \prec^c A \Rightarrow A^+ \prec^c A$

Proof:

Since A is EP_r and B is symmetric idempotent with rank r , both A and B are EP_r . By lemma 1, $R(A) = R(B) \Rightarrow A^+A = B^+B = B$ (since A^+A is the projection onto $R(A)$ along $N(A)$). Then (i) and (ii) follow from lemma 2. (iii) and (iv) follow from (i) and (ii) respectively and $B = B^+$.

Corollary 1:

Let A be EP_r , B be symmetric idempotent with rank r and $A \prec^c B$. Then $A^n \prec^c B \prec^c (A^n)^+$ for any positive integer n .

Proof:

Since $A \prec^c B$ and by theorem 1 (i), $B = B^+ \prec^c A^+$. Hence, $A \prec^c A^+$ follows from theorem 1 (iii). Since B is symmetric idempotent and by theorem B2 of [4p.433],

$A^2 \prec^c A^+A = B^+B = B$. Thus, $A^n \prec^c B$ is true for $n=2$. Now, $A^3 \prec^c BA = BB^+A = AA^+A = A \prec^c B$. Hence $A \prec^c B$. Thus, it is true for $n=3$. By continuing in this manner we can show that $A \prec^c B \Rightarrow A^n \prec^c B$ for any positive integer n . $B \prec^c (A^n)^+$ follows from $A^n \prec^c B$ and theorem 1(i). Hence the corollary.

Theorem 2:

Let A and B be EP_r matrices such that $AB = BA$. Then $A \prec^c B \Leftrightarrow B^+ \prec^c A^+$.

Proof:

Since A, B are EP_r and $A \prec^c B$, by lemma 1, $R(A) = R(B) = R(B^+)$. Since A and B^+ are EP_r and $R(A) = R(B^+)$, by theorem 3 and 4 of [1], AB^+ is EP_r and $(AB^+)^+ = BA^+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus, } AB^+ &= B^+A && \text{(by theorem 2 of [5])} && (1) \\ A \prec^c B &\Rightarrow AB^+ \prec^c BB^+ && \text{(by theorem B2 of [4,p.433])} \\ &\Rightarrow B^+A \prec^c BB^+ && \text{(by (1))} \\ &\Rightarrow BB^+ \prec^c (B^+A)^+ && \text{(by theorem 1(i) applied to } BB^+) \\ &\Rightarrow B^+B \prec^c A^+B \\ &\Rightarrow B^+BB^+ \prec^c A^+BB^+ \\ &\Rightarrow B^+ \prec^c A^+ \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, since A^+ and B^+ are EP_r . And by theorem 2 of [5], $BA^+ = A^+B$ is of rank r . In the above part, replacing A by B^+ and B by A^+ and using $(A^+)^+ = A, (B^+)^+ = B$,

We get $B^+ \prec^c A^+ \Rightarrow A \prec^c B$. Hence the theorem.

REMARK 4:

The condition on A and B that they have the same rank, but $AB \neq BA$ cannot hold in theorem 2. For example, consider,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 1/3 \begin{pmatrix} 12 & 3 & 3 \\ 11 & 12 & 10 \\ 7 & 12 & 11 \end{pmatrix} ; B = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 0 & 0 \\ 3 & 6 & 5 \\ 2 & 3 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \\ A^+ &= 1/45 \begin{pmatrix} 12 & 3 & -6 \\ -51 & 111 & -87 \\ 48 & -123 & 111 \end{pmatrix} ; B^+ = 1/15 \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 15 & -25 \\ -3 & -15 & 30 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Here $AB \neq BA$, however $A \prec^c B$, A and B are EP_r with rank 3 and $B^+ \prec^c A^+$.

Corollary 2:

Let A and B be EP_r matrices and $A \prec^c B$ such that $AB = BA$. Then $A^n \prec^c B^n$ for any positive integer n .

Proof:

By theorem B2 of [4, p.433] and $A \prec^c B$ we have $AB^+ \prec^c BB^+$. Since BB^+ is symmetric idempotent by theorem 1 (iii), we get

$$AB^+ \prec^c (AB^+)^+ = BA^+. \text{ By lemma 1, } AB^+A \prec^c BA^+A = B.$$

Using (1), we see that $AAB^+ \prec^c B$. By lemma 1, $A^+A = B^+B$.

Hence $A^2B^+B \prec^c B^2 \Rightarrow A^2 \prec^c B^2$. Thus the corollary is true for $n=2$.

Now, $A^2 \prec^c B^2 \Rightarrow A^3 \prec^c B^2A = AB^2 \prec^c BB^2 = B^3$

(Since $A \prec^c B \Rightarrow AB^2 \prec^c BB^2$). Thus it is true for $n = 3$. By continuing in this manner, we can show that $A \prec^c B \Rightarrow A^n \prec^c B^n$ for any positive integer n . Hence the corollary.

Theorem 3:

$$\text{Let } M = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \text{ with } \text{rank } M = \text{rank } A \text{ and } L = \begin{pmatrix} E & F \\ G & H \end{pmatrix} \text{ with}$$

$rank L = rank E$ be $n \times n$ real matrices such that $A^+B = E^+F$ (2)

Then $A \prec^c E$ and $C \prec^c G$.i.e., $A = R_1E$ and $C = R_2G \Leftrightarrow M \prec^c L$ with doubly stochastic matrix R of the form $\begin{pmatrix} O & R_1 \\ O & R_2 \end{pmatrix}$

Proof:

Since $M = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix}$ with $rank M = rank A$, where A is $k \times k$. and D is $(n-k) \times (n-k)$

matrices, by corollary in [3] it follows that $N(A) \subseteq N(C)$, $N(A^*) \subseteq N(B^*)$ and $D = CA^+B$ or equivalently, $C = CA^+A$, $B = AA^+B$ and $D = CA^+B$.

For L , we have $G = GE^+E$, $F = EE^+F$ and $H = GE^+F$. (3)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } A \prec^c E \text{ and } C \prec^c G &\Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} A & O \\ C & O \end{pmatrix} \prec^c \begin{pmatrix} E & O \\ G & O \end{pmatrix} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} A & O \\ C & O \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I & A^+B \\ O & I \end{pmatrix} \prec^c \begin{pmatrix} E & O \\ G & O \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I & A^+B \\ O & I \end{pmatrix} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \prec^c \begin{pmatrix} E & F \\ G & H \end{pmatrix} \\ &\Leftrightarrow M \prec^c L \end{aligned}$$

Hence the theorem.

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